

Carbon capture utilisation and storage technologies: Decarbonising hard-to-abate industries and strengthening strategic autonomy

Case study

Carbon4 Minerals:

Transforming CO₂ into added-value construction products

Fact sheet

Duration	1 January 2023 until 30 June 2027
EU contribution	€ 14 846 811,00
Type of action	Innovation Action
Coordinating organisation	Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (Belgium)
Consortium size	14 partners

Main objective of the project

The primary goal of Carbon4Minerals is to simultaneously use CO₂ from industrial flue gases and industrial waste streams (such as steel slags and construction/demolition waste) to produce innovative low-carbon binders and construction materials. This integrated approach is critical because it addresses three major environmental challenges at once, it reduces industrial CO₂ emissions; significantly reduces the carbon footprint of the building industry; and diverts large volumes of industrial waste from landfills. The project focuses on mineral carbonation, a process where CO₂ reacts with minerals to form carbonates and amorphous

silica. While the stable carbonates harden into high-value building products like bricks, pavers, and facade panels, the silica increases the reactivity of the materials for use as cement replacements.

A central pillar of the project is the deployment of eight industrial pilots across the entire CCU value chain. These pilots range from advancing CO₂ capture technologies using liquid and solid sorbents to producing low-carbon cement replacements (SCMs) and end-products that store CO₂ permanently within their structure.

Impact

The project is designed to deliver a transformative environmental impact on the construction sector:

Negative carbon footprint: The resulting materials aim for CO₂ emissions that are **80% to 135% lower** than traditional reference materials. In some instances, this results in a net uptake, where the product stores more CO₂ than was emitted during its production.

Industrial scalability: By capturing CO₂ directly from point sources (bricks, steel, and cement plants) and utilising it on-site, the project reduces the need for expensive purification and transport infrastructure required for traditional underground storage.

Resource efficiency: It unlocks a vast stock of currently underutilised waste resources, such as steel slags and fine particles from demolished buildings, to replace virgin raw materials.

End-product benefits compared to the industry standard: beyond having to meet rigorous safety and durability standards, these innovative construction materials offer enhanced aesthetic versatility through a wider range of colours and shades, alongside greater design flexibility and the unique benefit of permanent carbon storage within the mineral structure.

Connections to relevant EU policy

Carbon4Minerals is developing a practical and high-potential solution to simultaneously address several industrial challenges: the mitigation of process-inherent CO₂ emissions and the sustainable management of industrial waste streams, while ensuring the technology is both scalable and commercially viable. This approach serves as a technical enabler for the Clean Industrial Deal¹² and the Circular Economy Action Plan¹³. By converting industrial waste and captured CO₂ into valuable resources, it directly addresses the EU's mandate to decarbonise hard-to-abate sectors such as steel and cement, whilst supporting their competitiveness. These industries face process-inherent emissions that cannot be eliminated through electrification alone, making Carbon4Minerals' approach to mineralised storage a key component in reaching Europe's 2050 climate neutrality targets.

Status of implementation

As of February 2026, the project has successfully transitioned from design to active piloting and site testing. In the field of CO₂ capture, a mobile pilot using solid adsorption technology is being tested at VITO (Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek) using flue gases from its natural gas boiler, with plans to relocate to an

ArcelorMittal steel site by the end of 2026 to evaluate performance under industrial conditions. The pilots for low-carbon cements are also well-advanced; a carbonation clinker demonstration has already produced one tonne of material, while a Recycled Concrete Paste pilot led by Heidelberg Materials has been operational since mid-2025. In the final step of the CCU value chain, the pilot plant at Vandersanden is operational and producing bricks. Current efforts are focused on expanding the scope of input materials and testing new shapes for high-end products like facade and roof panels.

Next steps

The final phase of Carbon4Minerals will prioritise the rigorous validation of the new materials to ensure they meet the same longevity and safety standards as traditional construction products. Partners will conduct deep-dive durability assessments and update life cycle analyses with real-world data from the pilots to prove economic and environmental sustainability at an industrial scale.

Strategic planning for future deployment is already underway, including a geographic assessment to identify the best European sites for integrating these circular value chains.